

Gene	Maternal (Cp)	Zygotic UP	Expression @ 24hpf	Expression @ 48hpf
<i>ath-like</i>	no (36.17)	8-10	★	★
<i>hes3</i>	no (35.02)	10-12	n.d.	★
<i>foxD3-like</i>	no (40.00)	12-14	★	★
<i>sox10-like</i>	no (34.80)	12-14	★	★
<i>foxq2-like3</i>	yes (33.31)	16-18	★	★
<i>hox2</i>	no (40.00)	16-18	n.d.	★
<i>sox2</i>	no (40.00)	16-18	★	★
<i>coup-like1</i>	no (40.00)	18-20	★	★
<i>coup-like2</i>	yes (33.31)	18-20	★	★
<i>gfi-like</i>	no (38.94)	18-20	n.d.	★
<i>hd145</i>	no (40.00)	18-20	★	★
<i>tailless-like</i>	no (38.52)	18-20	n.d.	★
<i>vsx-like</i>	no (34.11)	18-20	★	★
<i>elav-like</i>	yes (28.66)	18-20	n.d.	★
<i>dkk3-like3</i>	no (36.65)	20-24	n.d.	★
<i>pea3-like</i>	no (36.87)	20-24	★	★
<i>paxA</i>	yes (31.57)	20-24	★	★
<i>gcm</i>	no (40.00)	20-24	★	★
<i>ashA</i>	no (40.00)	20-24	★	★
<i>vegf-like1</i>	yes (29.38)	n.d.	n.d.	★
<i>hd052</i>	no (37.65)	n.d.	★	★
<i>hes-like3</i>	-	-	★	★
<i>emxLX</i>	-	-	n.d.	★
<i>elav</i>	-	-	★	★
<i>anRFamide</i>	-	-	★	★
<i>soxb(2)</i>	-	-	★	★

ectoderm - salt/pepper expression